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Closing the feedback loop in the transition from secondary to higher education

Tinne De Laet¹

Head Tutorial Services Engineering Science
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC), KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Tom Broos

Department of Computer Science & LESEC, KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Maarten Pinxten

Postdoc Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center, KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Carolien Van Soom

Head Tutorial Services Science
Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center (LESEC), KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

Greet Langie

vice-dean Faculty Engineering Technology & LESEC, KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

Against the background of the increasing need for skilled scientists and engineers, any hurdle in the study career of engineering students is undesired. One of the most important hurdles is the transition from secondary to higher education.

The situation at faculty of Engineering Science at KU Leuven, the largest Flemish (Dutch-speaking part of Belgium) University, is not different. Even more, due to regional regulations, Flemish universities have to accept any student with a secondary education diploma into in the engineering bachelor program, even if the secondary education program does not provide the student with the required knowledge and

¹ Corresponding Author
Tinne De Laet
tinne.delaet@kuleuven.be

competencies. The resulting heterogeneous inflow of students creates an additional challenge.

During the last six years, researchers, educational staff and study advisors of the engineering science program of KU Leuven have collaborated to tackle this challenge. The concept paper will present the overarching ideas around the work that has been performed and provide pointers to the different supporting publications. Hereby, it will offer the unique opportunity for highlighting the connections between the work of our research team and the vision that underlies this work.

This paper seeks to inspire practitioners and researcher in the engineering education field who focus on the transition from secondary to higher education. More specifically, the paper aims to share the underlying vision and shows how a close collaboration between practitioners and researchers can create an added value and impact on the engineering education field.

1 INTRODUCTION

A European Parliament 2015 report on the creation of a competitive labour market emphasises the increasing need for STEM profiles: “... *the EU faces a shortage of skills in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), while it has an over-supply of social science graduates.*” It furthermore states that “*supplementary initiatives at European and national level are necessary to respond to the bottlenecks in STEM-related jobs and studies*”. This clarifies the importance of identifying hurdles in the career of engineering students and developing solutions to minimize these hurdles.

In the career towards engineering, the transition from secondary to higher education is one of the important hurdles [1], [2]. In the transition three phases are typically distinguished, the recruitment phase and activities, examination and application phase, and the registration phase. This paper focuses on the examination and application phase and the first weeks in higher education itself. The actual transition is heavily influenced by the local context, regional and national regulations, and culture. The ATTRACT project [3] has studied the three transition phases in five European countries (Belgium, Finland, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, and Sweden). The project showed that the formal admission requirements both on the level of general admission requirements (school certificate exams, ongoing performance at second-level, entrance exams, ...) and additional admission requirements for engineering courses (maths, physics, chemistry, biology) strongly differ between the participating European countries. Beside formal admission requirements, also academic and social challenges influence the transition [4]. While students are aware of the need to adapt their study and learning strategies to the new context of higher education, which adaptations are required and to what extent is less clear. Moreover, the new social context poses an additional challenge as students lack a comparative framework of peers in the first weeks of higher education (social-comparison theory [5]).

Feedback has shown to be supportive for student achievement especially when the type of feedback is adapted to the purpose and the circumstances [6]. Feedback

during the transition from secondary to higher education, which is the focus of this paper, has been shown to impact student motivation, confidence, retention, and success [7], [8].

2 CONTEXT

As context influences the transition from secondary to higher education, this section clarifies the context of higher education and the Engineering Sciences programme at KU Leuven. Higher education in Flanders operates in the bachelor-master-structure, the ECTS-system, and the European Qualification framework [9]. Students are directly admitted to professional or academic bachelor's programmes when they have a diploma of secondary education or a (foreign) diploma declared equivalent (except for medicine and dentistry and some programs in performing arts). In this open-admission system, students are permitted to enter any bachelor program independent of their program in secondary education. Entering the Bachelor of Engineering Science therefore does not formally require a strong preparation in mathematics and/or sciences. Tuition fees at KU Leuven are around 1000 euro for one academic year. The open-admission policy results in a more heterogeneous population regarding prior knowledge and skills, which poses challenges to the actual teaching and guidance of students. Not surprisingly the drop-out in the Bachelor of Engineering Science is around 40%.

Interestingly, until 2004 a multi-topic entrance exam existed for Engineering Science in Flanders, which stimulated, as a preparation, a high level of mathematics education in secondary schools and contributed to an international high reputation of the Flemish mathematics secondary school education [10]. Before abolishment of the entrance exam, the first-year success rate was around 70%. After abolishment, the success rate dropped to less than 50%.

Engineering Science programmes identified the need for a positioning test, assessing the mathematical skills of students before entering the bachelor program. In 2013, the three Flemish universities offering the Bachelor of Engineering Science started with such a positioning test, called 'ijkingstoets' (www.ijkingstoets.be). The test, typically consisting of 30 multiple choice questions, taken on paper and pencil during two sessions in summer, measures the ability of aspiring engineering students to solve engineering problems and compares a participant's mathematical skills with the required prior knowledge. The goal of the test is threefold: first, to encourage students that succeed; second, to stimulate students that are less successful to better prepare themselves by entering a remediation trajectory; third, to advise students that badly fail against entering the engineering studies. After a decision of the Flemish Parliament, participation to the positioning test became mandatory in the year 2018-2019 for all students wanting to subscribe to the Bachelor Engineering Science. Whereas participation is mandatory, the test is still non-binding: students that do not pass the test can still subscribe to the program.

3 CLOSING THE FEEDBACK LOOP

After clarifying the context, we will now provide more details on how our work of the last six years has been able to close the feedback loop in the transition from secondary to higher education. Remind that based on literature, we know that providing feedback in the transition from secondary to higher education can support a successful transition. The opportunities for providing feedback and the available data to provide feedback on are however limited.

Since 2013, the so-called 'ijkkingstoets' allows to provide feedback to aspiring engineering students regarding their mathematical skills and preparedness. The first line of research, elaborated on in Section 4, focused on the **predictive power of the positioning test** for first-year engineering student success. This predictive power was considered an important prerequisite to provide high-quality feedback to the participants. The second line of research, elaborated on in Section 5, focused on the **additional predictive power of the positioning test, the importance of other skills, and the confidence and beliefs** regarding first-year students success of aspiring engineering students.

The third line of research, elaborated on in Section 6, focused on **the feedback itself after the positioning test**. On the one hand it showed how a **learning dashboard** provides participants with feedback after the positioning test and how **predictive models** can be used to provide interpretable insights.

The fourth line of research, elaborated on in Section 7, is the one that closes the feedback loop. It showed that **activity on feedback dashboards** (third line of research) has **predictive power for student success** itself (second line of research) and therefore creates a useful data source that provides a new opportunity for feedback.

4 PREDICTIVE POWER OF THE POSITIONING TEST

At the SEFI 2013 conference, a first paper was published on the rationale, development, and first-results of the positioning test [11]. As the main goal of the positioning test was to provide feedback to aspiring student regarding their mathematical skills, subsequent research focused on the predictive power of the positioning test for first-year student success [12] and the impact of the positioning test on female students and students with disabilities [13].

The results showed that the obtained score on the positioning test is strongly **correlated with first-year students success** and that the test in particular allows to detect students who have little chance of succeeding in the bachelor [12]. Passing the positioning test is a positive indicator but no guarantee for student success, it was hypothesized that other factors such as motivation, study effort, study method, and stress-handling are still important to this end [12].

Despite its predictive power, the positioning test does not succeed in advising students who badly fail the test, to reconsider their initial choice: less than half of the students that obtain a positioning test score lower than 5/20 eventually decide not to enrol in

the Bachelor of Engineering Science [12]. After enrolment, these students experience big difficulties in catching up on basic mathematics while studying new course [12]. The impact of the positioning test on female students and students with disabilities was studied separately due to the underrepresentation of female students in Engineering Science (15%) and the importance of providing equal opportunities to all students. Students with disabilities scored equally well on the positioning test, while female students obtained lower scores. These lower scores were partially explained by a weaker mathematical preparation in secondary education and the higher number of blank answers, which according to literature originates from the behaviour of more risk-averse female students in multiple choice tests with negative marking [13]. As a consequence we started a research line on alternative scoring schemes for multiple-choice exams that do not affect risk-averse students [14]–[17]. No difference between male and female students with similar grades was observed regarding the decision to enrol after participation to the positioning test [13].

5 SKILLS, CONFIDENCE AND BELIEFS

Beside mathematical skills, learning and studying skills [18] and self-reported confidence in math/science ability and beliefs in future career opportunities [19] have been shown to be supportive for student success. Learning and studying skills measured using the Learning and Study Strategies Inventory (LASSI) differ significantly between UK, Belgium, and Slovakia due to the strong differences in educational context, including admission procedures and rules [20]. The educational context has also shown to affect the beliefs of students in student success [21]. Students in all contexts, however, believed that most academic activities (attending classes, studying hard, following-up student e-mail, etc.) are important for first-year student success. As learning and studying skills are supportive for student success and as students believe they are indeed important to be successful, they provide an important opportunity for feedback.

Fig. 1: Sankey diagram visualising the predictive power of the score on the positioning test for 1st semester student success, measured as study efficiency (percentage of successfully obtained credits from the booked ones).

In that respect, the **additional predictive power of learning and studying skills** is important. To this end, KU Leuven studied the incremental predictive power of these skills on top of prior academic achievement and score on the positioning test [22]. They showed that students' motivation/persistence, concentration, and time management skills at the start significantly influenced student achievement at the end of the first year, although the incremental value over prior achievement, measured as the number of hours of mathematics and mathematic GPA in secondary education, was small. Despite the small incremental value, feedback on learning and studying skills is still valuable as they offer opportunities for remedial interventions [22].

6 FEEDBACK REGARDING POSITIONING TEST

The feedback after the positioning test has evolved strongly since the start of the test in 2013. First, the feedback consisted of a personal **email** containing the obtained score, the provided answers, and a link to an **online document** containing a histogram that allowed the participants to compare their own score with the other participants and the correct answers for each of the multiple-choice question. Later, as the study results of the participants were available and the predictive power (Section 4) was proven, visualisations showing the relation between the score on the positioning test and later student success were added (Fig. 1).

Oefening 25

Een voederbak heeft een lengte van 1,2 m, is op het breedste punt 0,5 m breed en op het diepste punt 0,5 m diep, zoals aangeduid op onderstaande figuur. Elke dwarsdoorsnede evenwijdig met het getekende vooraanzicht is identiek en heeft een parabolische vorm die symmetrisch is t.o.v. een verticale as. Wat is de inhoud van deze voederbak?

- (A) 0,2 m³
- (B) 0,24 m³
- (C) 0,28 m³
- (D) 0,3 m³

Fig. 2: Feedback on one question of the positioning test. The current student provided answer B (indicated by the boxed answer), which is wrong. The correct answer is A. Each dot represents the answer of one participant.

In 2018, a **feedback dashboard** [23] was developed within the STELA project (stela-project.eu) that provided additional feedback. A demo-version of the dashboard can be accessed at <https://feedback.ijkingstoets.be/ijkingstoets-11-ir-ignore/feedback.html?fc=11ir0demo> Participants are provided with more details on how other participants answered each question (Fig. 2). The dashboard furthermore provides feedback regarding prior academic achievement of the student (GPA of mathematics in secondary education and study advice of the teacher board), and three learning skills (motivation, concentration, and time management), which were measured using a questionnaire, including three scales of the LASSI questionnaire, during the positioning test. For each of these dimensions the participant receives a visualization showing how he/she positions with respect to the other participants, and how this dimension relates to student success.

After the positioning test, students received a link and personal login to the dashboard. Furthermore, student guidance counsellors of the faculty could, after permission of the participant, use the dashboard during a personal feedback conversation [23]. Further research focuses on how the feedback can be optimized and whether a more textual or visual presentation is most effective [24].

Fig. 3: Example of the output of LIME (Local Interpretable Model Agnostic Explanations) when predicting if a student is at risk (grade point average ≤ 8.5) or not (grade point average > 8.5). The probability that the student is at risk is 84%. The blue factors contribute to the student being predicted as at risk: lower prior academic achievement in physics (phy), chemistry (chem), mathematics (math), and low preference for pressure (press) and goal strategies (goal). On the positive side (orange) the student had a high number of hours mathematics in secondary education (hrs) and low to medium affective strategies (affe). The numbers indicate to which extent the factors contribute to the prediction.

The current feedback is limited to descriptive feedback, visualized to support the interpretation by the users. This feedback is provided for each of the dimensions (positioning test score, prior academic achievement, and learning skills) separately. **Predictive models** have the potential to combine these different dimensions into an overall score that represents the ‘odds of success’ of the student in the bachelor. However, such predictive models are only useful when they provide interpretable insights. We found that existing techniques such as LIME [25] can be used to create visual insights on the contribution of each of the individual factors to the prediction (*Fig. 3*). As a result, the user can interpret what dimensions are contributing to the potential success of the student and what dimensions contribute to the potential drop-out [25]. Future work consists of testing if the resulting visualization can be used by student advisors during a feedback conversation, if the visualizations provide added value to the descriptive feedback, and if a dashboard can be developed based on the visualizations.

7 FEEDBACK USAGE AS A PREDICTOR FOR STUDENT SUCCESS

On top of the feedback in the positioning test dashboard, a learning dashboard was also developed to provide students with feedback on their learning skills in the first weeks of higher education. After completing the LASSI survey in the first week of the academic year, students received a link to their individual dashboard providing feedback on motivation, concentration, performance anxiety, use of test-strategies and time management. A demo is available at: <https://learninganalytics.set.kuleuven.be/static-demo-lassi/>. We showed that the use of the dashboard positively relates to first-semester student success, both for the positioning test dashboard [25] and for the LASSI dashboard [26], [27] and that this dashboard usage has additional predictive power for first-semester student success [under review]. This means that the deployment of feedback dashboard creates useful learning traces, i.e. new data reflecting the engagement of the student with the programme, that can again be used as a source for feedback. In short: use of feedback creates an opportunity for feedback. This is a valuable finding considering the sparsity of the data sources in the transition from secondary to higher education.

8 CONCLUSION & FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

This paper provided an overview of the research and work performed to support the transition between secondary and higher education at the Bachelor of Engineering Science, KU Leuven. This paper hereby not only provides an helicopter view to the work performed but also shows how a close collaboration between practitioners and researchers can create impact on the engineering education field. We believe that the paper can inspire other practitioners and researchers in the engineering education field that focus on the transition from secondary to higher education.

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